

SHEAR-DEFORMATION FINITE ELEMENTS FOR THE FINITE-ROTATION ANALYSIS OF ARBITRARY COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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Abstract For arbitrary multilayered shell structures made particularly of composite material a refined finite-rotation theory with 7 independent displacement variables is developed by means of a cubic series expansion of the displacement field in thickness coordinate. Procedures are given permitting a unique determination of the first order displacement term in the case of finite rotations. Kinematic relations are formulated in a form suitable for isoparametric finite element formulation. This third order single-layer theory contains as special case a Mindlin-Reissner type theory which is generalized to a layer-wise model being more predictive in dealing with local interlaminar effects. Both theoretical models are transformed into isoparametric finite shell elements and then compared on an appropriate example concerning their prediction capability of interlaminar shear stresses. Also an example is given demonstrating their applicability to finite-rotation phenomena.

Keywords: finite rotations, composite laminate, layer-wise analysis model, third-order single-layer model, isoparametric formulation

1. INTRODUCTION

Due to their beneficial properties advanced composite laminates have been, in recent years, increasingly used in many engineering structures and thereby stimulated considerable interest in the development of analysis models of a special precision. The strong anisotropy of each lamina and discontinuity in material properties across the interfaces make the classical laminate theories inadequate for the analysis of this structure class. Therefore, many attempts have been made to develop refined laminate theories and numerical models [1-5] with the aim to improve the analysis accuracy in prediction of the global behaviour, particularly the local effects such as interlaminar shear stresses.

In this paper, a third order single-layer theory, a layer-wise theory [6,7] and the corresponding finite element models are presented. Suitable numerical examples are given to compare the prediction capability of different theories and to demonstrate the applicability of the finite element models proposed to strongly nonlinear problems.

2. THE THIRD-ORDER SHELL THEORY

Shell equations will be presented in tensor notation. As usual, Greek indices represent the numbers 1, 2 and Latin ones the numbers 1, 2, 3. Points of the middle surface \bar{F} are determined by curvilinear coordinates θ^α . Geometrical variables referring to the undeformed state are denoted by the suffix (\circ) and those associated with the deformed state without supplementary marks. The notation $(\dots)^*$ characterizes variables of the shell continuum depending on the thickness coordinate θ^3 .

The position vector \mathbf{r}^* of an arbitrary point P^* of the deformed shell continuum is approximated in the present theory by a cubic series expansion in thickness coordinate θ^3 as follows [6, 7]

$$\mathbf{r}^*(\theta^i) = \mathbf{r} + \theta^3 \mathbf{a}_3 + (\theta^3)^3 \mathbf{y} \quad , \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{r} is the position vector of the deformed middle surface F , \mathbf{a}_3 a unit vector and finally \mathbf{y} a vector supposed to be perpendicular to \mathbf{a}_3 . The cited constraints for \mathbf{a}_3 and \mathbf{y} imply that elongations in θ^3 -direction are omitted. According to the isoparametric concept the vectors \mathbf{r} and \mathbf{a}_3 are decomposed with respect to a fixed Cartesian reference frame \mathbf{i}_i while the undeformed middle surface basis $\hat{\mathbf{a}}_i$ is used for the decomposition of the third order displacement vector \mathbf{y} , thus

$$\mathbf{r} = X^k \mathbf{i}_k \quad , \quad \mathbf{a}_3 = A^k \mathbf{i}_k \quad , \quad \mathbf{y} = Y^i \hat{\mathbf{a}}_i \quad . \quad (2)$$

Introducing the expression (1) and its undeformed counterpart $\hat{\mathbf{r}}^* = \hat{\mathbf{r}} + \theta^3 \hat{\mathbf{a}}_3$ into the well-known Green's strain tensor

$$\gamma_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{r}^*_{,i} \cdot \mathbf{r}^*_{,j} - \hat{\mathbf{r}}^*_{,i} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{r}}^*_{,j}) \quad (3)$$

leads by virtue of (2) to

$$\gamma_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} \gamma_{\alpha\beta} & \gamma_{\alpha 3} \\ \gamma_{3\alpha} & \gamma_{33} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \sum_{n=0}^3 (\theta^3)^n \overset{n}{\gamma}_{\alpha\beta} & \sum_{k=0,2} (\theta^3)^k \overset{k}{\gamma}_{\alpha 3} \\ \sum_{k=0,2} (\theta^3)^k \overset{k}{\gamma}_{\alpha 3} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

with 2D strains $\overset{n}{\gamma}_{\alpha\beta}$ and $\overset{m}{\gamma}_{\alpha 3}$ defined as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \overset{0}{\gamma}_{\alpha\beta} &= \frac{1}{2} (X^i_{,\alpha} X^j_{,\beta} - \hat{X}^i_{,\alpha} \hat{X}^j_{,\beta}) \delta_{ij} \quad , \\ \overset{1}{\gamma}_{\alpha\beta} &= \frac{1}{2} (X^i_{,\alpha} A^j_{,\beta} + X^i_{,\beta} A^j_{,\alpha} - \hat{X}^i_{,\alpha} \hat{A}^j_{,\beta} - \hat{X}^i_{,\beta} \hat{A}^j_{,\alpha}) \delta_{ij} \quad , \\ \overset{2}{\gamma}_{\alpha\beta} &= \frac{1}{2} (A^i_{,\alpha} A^j_{,\beta} - \hat{A}^i_{,\alpha} \hat{A}^j_{,\beta}) \delta_{ij} \quad , \\ \overset{3}{\gamma}_{\alpha\beta} &= \frac{1}{2} [\hat{X}^i_{,\rho} (X^j_{,\alpha} Y^\rho_{,\beta} + X^j_{,\beta} Y^\rho_{,\alpha}) + \hat{A}^i (X^j_{,\alpha} Y^3_{,\beta} + X^j_{,\beta} Y^3_{,\alpha}) \\ &\quad + Y^3 (\hat{A}^i_{,\alpha} X^j_{,\beta} + \hat{A}^i_{,\beta} X^j_{,\alpha})] \delta_{ij} \quad , \\ \overset{0}{\gamma}_{\alpha 3} &= \frac{1}{2} X^i_{,\alpha} A_j \delta_{ij} \quad , \\ \overset{2}{\gamma}_{\alpha 3} &= \frac{3}{2} (\hat{X}^i_{,\rho} X^j_{,\alpha} Y^\rho + \hat{A}^i X^j_{,\alpha} Y^3) \delta_{ij} \quad . \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

The notation $(\dots)^n$ with $n=0,1,2,3$ indicates the order of the strains in the above series expansions (4). For an *a priori* satisfaction of the unit length condition $\mathbf{a}_3 \cdot \mathbf{a}_3 = 1$, the components A^i occurring in (5) are expressed in terms of the Euler rotational variables ψ_α [8] as

$$A^1 = \sin \psi_1 \cos \psi_2, \quad A^2 = \sin \psi_1 \sin \psi_2, \quad A^3 = \cos \psi_1. \quad (6)$$

For later use it is suitable to introduce the difference vector $\mathbf{w} = \mathbf{a}_3 - \hat{\mathbf{a}}_3 = w^i \hat{\mathbf{a}}_i$, satisfying the transformations

$$w_\alpha = (A^i - \hat{A}^i) \hat{X}_{,\alpha}^j \delta_{ij}, \quad w_3 = A^i \hat{A}^j \delta_{ij} - 1. \quad (7)$$

Thus, the constraint $\mathbf{a}_3 \cdot \mathbf{y} = 0$ for the variable \mathbf{y} yields

$$Y^\alpha w_\alpha + Y^3 (1 + w_3) = 0, \quad (8)$$

permitting the calculation of the dependent component Y^3 in terms of the independent ones Y^α .

In terms of the 2D strain variables (4) the internal virtual work of the laminate is given by [6]

$$\delta^* A_i = - \iint_{\hat{F}} \left(\sum_{n=0}^3 \hat{S}^{(n\alpha\beta)} \delta \gamma_{\alpha\beta}^n + 2 \sum_{m=0,2} \hat{S}^{(m\alpha 3)} \delta \gamma_{\alpha 3}^m \right) d\hat{F}, \quad (9)$$

where $\hat{S}^{(n\alpha\beta)}$ and $\hat{S}^{(m\alpha 3)}$ are the conjugate force variables. For an arbitrary laminate consisting of N orthotropic layers, their relations to the 2D strains are given by the following constitutive equations

$$\hat{S}^{(n\alpha\beta)} = \sum_{j=0}^3 C^{\alpha\beta\rho\lambda j} \gamma_{\rho\lambda}^j \quad (n = 0,1,2,3), \quad \hat{S}^{(m\alpha 3)} = \sum_{i=0,2}^{i+m} C^{\alpha\rho i} \gamma_{\rho 3}^i \quad (m = 0,2). \quad (10)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} C^{\alpha\beta\rho\lambda k} &= \sum_{L=1}^N \int_{z_L^1}^{z_L^u} \hat{\mu} C_L^{\alpha\beta\rho\lambda} (\theta^3)^k d\theta^3 \quad (k = 0,1,2,\dots,6), \\ C^{\alpha\rho} &= \sum_{L=1}^N \int_{z_L^1}^{z_L^u} \hat{\mu} C_L^{\alpha\rho} (\theta^3)^1 d\theta^3 \quad (l = 0,2,4) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

and the index L indicates a variable referring to the L -th layer. For the calculation of tensorial coefficients $C_L^{\alpha\beta\rho\lambda}$ and $C_L^{\alpha\rho}$ in terms of the given material properties we refer to the detailed derivation [6, 7] and note that $\hat{\mu}$ is approximated in the numerical procedure by 1. By introducing suitable constraints the above third-order theory can easily be specialized to classical theories of Mindlin-Reissner and Kirchhoff-Love types. Details concerning this aspect is given in [6, 7].

3. A LAYERWISE THEORY

This theoretical model is based on a subdivision of the laminate into N sub-elements across the thickness such that at least one sub-element per layer is used. Each sub-element L ($L=1, 2, \dots, N$) is described by the Mindlin-Reissner type theory, imposing C^o -displacement continuities on all interfaces. Accordingly, this concept leads to a theoretical model with $2N+3$ independent displacement variables in the case of N sub-elements across the thickness. As each sub-element is allowed to possess two independent rotational variables

$\psi_{\alpha L}$, laminates of dissimilar material layers can be considered by this model in any desired accuracy order by an adequate subdivision.

To describe this model the attention is first focused to the sub-element L . The variables associated with it will be denoted by $(\dots)_L$. The position vector \mathbf{r}_L^* of an arbitrary point P_L^* of the deformed sub-element L is described by the linear approximation

$$\mathbf{r}_L^* = \mathbf{r}_L + \xi_L^3 \mathbf{a}_{3L}, \quad (12)$$

where $\xi_L^3 (-\frac{h_L}{2} \leq \xi_L^3 \leq \frac{h_L}{2})$ is the distance of an arbitrary point P_L^* from the middle surface \mathring{F}_L of the sub-element L , measured in $\mathring{\mathbf{a}}_3$ -direction. The vectors \mathbf{r}_L and \mathbf{a}_{3L} entering in (12) are decomposed with respect to the global Cartesian reference frame \mathbf{i}_i :

$$\mathbf{r}_L = X_L^i \mathbf{i}_i, \quad \mathbf{a}_{3L} = A_L^i \mathbf{i}_i \quad (13)$$

which is suitable for the isoparametric formulation of the kinematic relations.

Since the position vectors \mathbf{r}_L^* ($L = 2, \dots, N$) of the deformed laminate are subjected to continuity conditions on all sub-element interfaces

$$\mathbf{r}_L^* (\xi_L^3 = -\frac{h_L}{2}) = \mathbf{r}_{L-1}^* (\xi_{L-1}^3 = +\frac{h_{L-1}}{2}) \quad (14)$$

the position vector \mathbf{r}_L occurring in (12) is a dependent variable and can be, by means of (12) and (13), described by the following expression:

$$\mathbf{r}_L = \mathbf{r}_1 + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{K=1}^{L-1} (h_K \mathbf{a}_{3K} + h_{K+1} \mathbf{a}_{3(K+1)}) \quad (15)$$

Accordingly, the position vector \mathbf{r}_L ($L = 2, \dots, N$) depends on the position vector \mathbf{r}_1 of the first sub-element and the deformed directors \mathbf{a}_{3K} of all foregoing sub-elements K from 1 to L . Under consideration of (13) eqn (15) can be expressed in terms of the components X_K^i and A_K^i ($K = 1, 2, \dots, L$). Also in the present model, the variables A_K^i are, according to (6), to be transformed into the independent rotational variables $\psi_{\alpha K}$ in order to satisfy the constraint $\mathbf{a}_{3K} \cdot \mathbf{a}_{3K} = 1$ *a priori*.

The deformation state of the sub-element L is described, as in the Mindlin Reissner type theory, by the tangential strains $\alpha_{\alpha\beta L} = \overset{0}{\gamma}_{\alpha\beta L}$, $\beta_{\alpha\beta L} = \overset{1}{\gamma}_{\alpha\beta L}$ and the shear strains $\gamma_{\alpha L} = 2 \overset{0}{\gamma}_{\alpha 3L}$. The corresponding kinematic relations in isoparametric form of the sub-element L can be adopted from (5) by using the notation $(\dots)_L$, e.g.:

$$\alpha_{\alpha\beta L} = \frac{1}{2} (X_{L,\alpha}^i X_{L,\beta}^j - \overset{\circ}{X}_{L,\alpha}^i \overset{\circ}{X}_{L,\beta}^j) \delta_{ij} \quad (16)$$

In view of (15), (16) the internal virtual work of the laminate can be obtained by summing up the virtual work of the sub-elements 1 to N as follows [7]:

$$\delta^* A_i = \sum_{L=1}^N \delta^* A_{iL} = - \sum_{L=1}^N \int \int_{\mathring{F}_1} (\overset{0}{S}_L^{(\alpha\beta)} \delta \alpha_{(\alpha\beta)L} + \overset{1}{S}_L^{(\alpha\beta)} \delta \beta_{(\alpha\beta)L} + \overset{0}{S}_L^{\alpha 3} \delta \gamma_{\alpha L}) \sqrt{\overset{\circ}{\mathbf{a}}_L / \overset{\circ}{\mathbf{a}}_1} d\mathring{F}_1 \quad (17)$$

where the multiplier $\sqrt{\overset{\circ}{\mathbf{a}}_L / \overset{\circ}{\mathbf{a}}_1}$ indicates a surface integration over the reference surface \mathring{F}_1 of the first sub-element.

4. ASSUMED STRAIN SHELL ELEMENTS

The third order theory RT7 and the layer-wise theory LWT are both transformed into 4-node isoparametric shell elements RT7-IAS4 and LWT-IAS4, respectively. To avoid locking the constant shear deformation term $\gamma_{\alpha 3}^0$ is interpolated in RT7-IAS4 according to the assumed strain concept (9). Higher order shear strains $\gamma_{\alpha 3}^2$ occurring in RT7 require no special treatment in this sense. Shear deformations $\gamma_{\alpha L}$ ($L=1, \dots, N$) occurring in the layer-wise theory (17) are interpolated in the same manner as $\gamma_{\alpha 3}^0$ in the model RT7. Main characteristics of both models are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Isoparametric assumed strain shell elements based on the third-order theory RT7 and the layer-wise theory LWT

	Isoparametric Assumed Strain Finite-Rotation Elements	
	RT7-IAS4	LWT-IAS4
Theoretical fundamentals	Third order theory (RT7)	Layer-wise theory (LWT)
Degrees of freedom	$\Delta X^i, \Delta \psi_\alpha, y^\alpha$ (7×4)	$\Delta X_1^i, \Delta \psi_{\alpha L}, L = 1, 2, \dots, N$ N: number of sub-elements across the thickness $(2N + 3) \times 4$
Interpolations for	$\Delta X^i, \Delta \psi_\alpha, y^\alpha$	$\Delta X_1^i, \Delta \psi_{\alpha L}, L = 1, 2, \dots, N$
	bilinear polynomials	
Integration points	2×2	2×2
Interpolations for $\frac{h}{\gamma_\alpha}$ or $\bar{\gamma}_{\alpha L}$	$\bar{\gamma}_{1L} = \xi^2 \gamma_{1L}^A + (1 - \xi^2) \gamma_{1L}^C$ $\bar{\gamma}_{2L} = \xi^1 \gamma_{2L}^D + (1 - \xi^1) \gamma_{2L}^B$	

5. NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

The first example is a sandwich plate under uniform transverse load q [10]. This square plate with a side-length to thickness ratio of $a/h = 10$ is simply supported along all four edges and consists of three layers placed symmetrically to the middle surface. The thickness of the face sheets is $0.01h$ and that of the core $0.08h$. The material constants of the core are: $E_1 = 0.897950$, $E_2 = 0.471425$, $\nu_{12} = 0.440461$, $G_{12} = 0.262931$, $G_{23} = 0.266810$ and $G_{13} = 0.159914$. A linear parameter study has been carried out by varying the modular ratio R , which represents the ratio of the material properties of the face sheets to those of the core. The numerical results are nondimensionalized by using the following multipliers: $m_4 = 1/q$ and $m_5 = E_1(\text{core})/[(1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21})hq]$. The results for the deflection $v_{3\max}$ ($\theta^1 = \theta^2 = a/2$), illustrated in Fig 1, show that the discrepancies between the different theoretical models are becoming increasingly significant as the parameter R increases. This is particularly the case if

Fig. 1 Influence of the modular ratio R on the displacement

the results due to the refined models RT7 and LWT are compared with those obtained by the classical models of Mindlin-Reissner and Kirchhoff-Love type.

The distribution of the transverse shear stress s^{13} across the thickness for $R = 10$ is illustrated in Fig 2, calculated by different analysis models. The results presented refer to the center point of the element near the plate corner. The piecewise constant distribution due to the layer-wise model LWT has been replaced by a smooth curve passing through the middle surface values of each sub-element. It is remarkable that this curve vanishes at the laminate faces, passes through the exact values by [10] and, more importantly, contains no discontinuities at the interfaces. These aspects demonstrate clearly the excellent prediction capability of the layer-wise theory in across-thickness modelling of interlaminar shear stresses. This capability is certainly due to the consideration of supplementary degrees of freedom in the layer-wise model which provide an *a priori* satisfaction of interlaminar equilibrium conditions. On the contrary, the s^{13} -distributions calculated by single-layer models involve large interlaminar discontinuities and are also not able to predict the maximum value with a sufficient accuracy.

The second example which shall demonstrate the applicability of the analysis models to arbitrary shell geometries and very strong nonlinearities is a hyperboloid of revolution under two pairs of opposite point loads. The material data and the lamination scheme are adopted from the first example, the shell thickness is chosen as $h = 0.10$. The throat radius is $r_T = 7.5$, the upper rim radius $r_O = 15.0$ and the total height of the structure $h_T = 40.0$. Due to the symmetry of material and geometry only one octant of the shell has been analyzed by 24×24 elements LWT-IAS4 and RT7-IAS4. The analysis has been carried out for the modular ratio $R = 10$. Three-dimensional plots of the undeformed and deformed configuration at load level $f = 2.25$ are presented in Fig 3. It can clearly be seen that the developed elements are able to grasp very large rotations and displacements which are involved in this example.

Fig. 2 Distribution of transverse shear stresses s^{13} across the thickness

Fig. 3 Hyperboloidal shell - undeformed and deformed configurations

6. CONCLUSIONS

A third order single-layer theory and a layer-wise theory have been presented in a single formulation and both transformed into 4-node isoparametric shell elements using the assumed strain concept to interpolate the constant shear strains. Both elements obtained are locking-free, insensitive to element distortions and applicable to strongly nonlinear situations.

The single-layer model is able to simulate the global deformation behaviour very accurately even in the case of very thick structures and strong anisotropy over the thickness. If a very accurate prediction of interlaminar effects such as transverse shear stresses are, however, required it should be replaced by the decisively more expensive layer-wise model. This last mentioned element has shown to be able to simulate interlaminar effects in every desired accuracy level by a suitable sub-element selection across the thickness.

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